

Title: The Slope stability analysis

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METHODS OF SOIL SLOP STABILITY ANALYSIS

Abstract: Slope failure is one of the major geological phenomenon that happen due to the topography and weather conditions which cause a wide range of ground movements which needed engineers to plan in order to avoid its risk on human lives and properties by an appropriate stabilizing method. The analysis of slope stability has received widely attention now days because of its practical importance. To provide steepest slops which are stable and safe various investigations are ongoing. Stability is determined by the balance of shear stress and shear strength. If the forces available to resist movement are greater than the forces driving movement, the slope is considered stable. A factor of safety is calculated by dividing the forces resisting movement by the forces driving movement. A previously stable slope may be initially affected by preparatory factors, making the slope conditionally unstable. The field of slope stability encompasses static and dynamic stability of slopes of earth and rock-fill dams, slopes of embankments, excavated slopes, and natural slopes in soil and soft rock. Various methods are available for slope stability analysis. This paper aims an overview on various methods of slope stability on the basis of assumptions, Factor of safety calculation, applicability of output of the method with its limitations. This paper also aims to focus some new mathematical tools which can be applicable for stability analysis of slope.

Keywords: Consideration and assumptions, Factor of safety, stability analysis, Slop of Finite Height, Taylor's stability, Method of slices for steady seepage, Numerical method.

1. Introduction

Slopes of earth are of two types

1. Natural slopes
2. Man made slopes

Natural slopes are those that exist in nature and are formed by natural causes. Such slopes exist in hilly areas. The sides of cuttings, the slopes of embankments constructed for roads, railway lines, canals etc. and the slopes of earth dams constructed for storing water are examples of man made slopes. The slopes whether natural or artificial may be

1. Infinite slopes
2. Finite slopes

The term infinite slope is used to designate a constant slope of infinite extent. The long slope of the face of a mountain is an example of this type, whereas finite slopes are limited in extent. The slopes of embankments and earth dams are examples of finite slopes. The slope length depends on the height of the dam or embankment.

Slope Stability: Slope stability is an extremely important consideration in the design and construction of earth dams. The stability of a natural slope is also important. The results of a slope failure can often be catastrophic, involving the loss of considerable property and many lives. Causes of Failure of Slopes: The important factors that cause instability in a slope and lead to failure are

1. Gravitational force
2. Force due to seepage water
3. Erosion of the surface of slopes due to flowing water
4. The sudden lowering of water adjacent to a slope
5. Forces due to earthquakes

The effect of all the forces listed above is to cause movement of soil from high points to low points. The most important of such forces is the component of gravity that acts in the direction of probable motion. The various effects of flowing or seeping water are generally recognized as very important in stability problems, but often these effects have not been properly identified. It is a fact that the seepage occurring within a soil mass causes seepage

Figure 1.1: Forces that act on earth slope.

forces, which have much greater effect than is commonly realized. Erosion on the surface of a slope may be the cause of the removal of a certain weight of soil, and may thus lead to an

increased stability as far as mass movement is concerned. On the other hand, erosion in the form of undercutting at the toe may increase the height of the slope, or decrease the length of the incipient failure surface, thus decreasing the stability. When there is a lowering of the ground water or of a freewater surface adjacent to the slope, for example in a sudden drawdown of the water surface in a reservoir there is a decrease in the buoyancy of the soil which is in effect an increase in the weight. This increase in weight causes increase in the shearing stresses that may or may not be in part counteracted by the increase in shearing strength, depending upon whether or not the soil is able to undergo compression which the load increase tends to cause. If a large mass of soil is saturated and is of low permeability, practically no volume changes will be able to occur except at a slow rate, and in spite of the increase of load the strength increase may be inappreciable. Shear at constant volume may be accompanied by a decrease in the intergranular pressure and an increase in the neutral pressure. A failure may be caused by such a condition in which the entire soil mass passes into a state of liquefaction and flows like a liquid. A condition of this type may be developed if the mass of soil is subject to vibration, for example, due to earthquake forces. The various forces that act on slopes are illustrated in Fig. 1.1

1. General Consideration and assumptions in the analysis

There are three distinct parts to an analysis of the stability of a slope They are:

1.1 Testing of samples to determine the cohesion and angle of internal friction

If the analysis is for a natural slope, it is essential that the sample be undisturbed. In such important respects as rate of shear application and state of initial consolidation, the condition of testing must represent as closely as possible the most unfavorable conditions ever likely to occur in the actual slope.

1.2 The study of items which are known to enter but which cannot be accounted for in the computations.

The most important of such items is progressive cracking which will start at the top of the slope where the soil is in tension, and aided by water pressure, may progress to considerable depth. In addition, there are the effects of the non-homogeneous nature of the typical soil and other variations from the ideal conditions which must be assumed.

1.3 Computation

If a slope is to fail along a surface, all the shearing strength must be overcome along that surface which then becomes a surface of rupture. Any one such as ABC in Fig.1 (b) represents one of an infinite number of possible traces on which failure might occur. It is assumed that the problem is two dimensional, which theoretically requires a long length of slope normal to the section. However, if the cross section investigated holds for a running length of roughly

two or more times the trace of the rupture, it is probable that the two dimensional case holds within the required accuracy. The shear strength of soil is assumed to follow Coulomb's law

$$s = c' + \sigma' \tan \phi'$$

where,

c' = effective unit cohesion

σ' = effective normal stress on the surface of rupture = $(\sigma - u)$

σ = total normal stress on the surface of rupture

u = pore water pressure on the surface of rupture

ϕ' = effective angle of internal friction.

The item of great importance is the loss of shearing strength which many clays show when subjected to a large shearing strain. The stress-strain curves for such clays show the stress rising with increasing strain to a maximum value, after which it decreases and approaches an ultimate value which may be much less than the maximum. Since a rupture surface tends to develop progressively rather than with all the points at the same state of strain, it is generally the ultimate value that should be used for the shearing strength rather than the maximum value.

2. Factor of safety

In stability analysis, two types of factors of safety are normally used. They are

1. Factor of safety with respect to shearing strength.
2. Factor of safety with respect to cohesion. This is termed the factor of safety with respect to height.

Let,

F_S = factor of safety with respect to strength

F_C = factor of safety with respect to cohesion

F_H = factor of safety with respect to height

F_ϕ = factor of safety with respect to friction

C'_M = mobilized cohesion

ϕ'_M = mobilized angle of friction

τ = average value of mobilized shearing strength

s = maximum shearing strength.

The factor of safety with respect to shearing strength, F_S , may be written as

$$F_S = \frac{S}{\tau} = \frac{C' + \sigma' \tan \phi'}{\tau}$$

The shearing strength mobilized at each point on a failure surface may be written as

$$\tau = \frac{c'}{F_S} + \sigma' \frac{\tan \phi'}{F_S}$$

$$\text{Or, } \tau = C'_m + \sigma' \tan \phi'_m \dots \dots \dots (2.1)$$

$$\text{Where, } C'_m = \frac{C'}{F_s}, \tan \phi'_m = \frac{\tan \phi'}{F_s}$$

Actually the shearing resistance (mobilized value of shearing strength) does not develop to a like degree at all points on an incipient failure surface. The shearing strains vary considerably and the shearing stress may be far from constant. However the above expression is correct on the basis of average conditions.

If the factors of safety with respect to cohesion and friction are different, we may write the equation of the mobilized shearing resistance as

$$\tau = \frac{C'}{F_c} + \sigma' \frac{\tan \phi'}{F_\phi}$$

It will be shown later on that F_c depends on the height of the slope. From this it may be concluded that the factor of safety with respect to cohesion may be designated as the factor of safety with respect to height. This factor is denoted by F_H and it is the ratio between the critical height and the actual height, the critical height being the maximum height at which it is possible for a slope to

be stable. We may write from

$$\tau = \frac{C'}{F_H} + \sigma' \tan \phi' \dots \dots \dots (2.2)$$

where F_ϕ is arbitrarily taken equal to unity.

3. STABILITY ANALYSIS OF INFINITE SLOPES IN SAND OR CLAY.

3.1 STABILITY ANALYSIS OF INFINITE SLOPES IN SAND

As an introduction to slope analysis, the problem of a slope of infinite extent is of interest. Imagine an infinite slope, as shown in Fig. 3.1, making an angle β with the horizontal. The soil is cohesionless and completely homogeneous throughout. Then the stresses acting on any vertical plane in the soil are the same as those on any other vertical plane. The stress at any point on a plane EF parallel to the surface at depth z will be the same as at every point on this plane.

Now consider a vertical slice of material ABCD having a unit dimension normal to the page. The forces acting on this slice are its weight W, a vertical reaction R on the base of the slice, and two lateral forces P_1 acting on the sides. Since the slice is in equilibrium, the weight and reaction are equal in magnitude and opposite in direction. They have a common line of action which passes through the center of the base AB. The lateral forces must be equal and opposite and their line of action must be parallel to the sloped surface.

The normal and shear stresses on plane AB are

$$\sigma'_n = \gamma z \cos^2 \beta$$

$$\tau = \gamma z \cos^2 \beta$$

Where, σ'_n = effective normal stress,
 γ = effective unit weight of the sand.

If full resistance is mobilized on plane AB, the shear strength, s , of the soil per Coulomb's law is

$$S = \sigma'_n \tan \phi'$$

when $\tau = S$, substituting for s and σ'_n , we have,

$$\gamma z \cos \beta = \gamma z \cos^2 \beta \tan \phi'$$

Figure 3.1 Stability analysis of infinite slope in sand

$$\text{or } \tan \beta = \tan \phi' \dots \dots \dots (3.1)$$

Equation (3.1) indicates that the maximum value of β is limited to ϕ' if the slope is to be stable. This condition holds true for cohesionless soils whether the slope is completely dry or completely submerged under water.

The factor of safety of infinite slopes in sand may be written as

$$F_s = \frac{\tan \phi'}{\tan \beta}$$

3.2 STABILITY ANALYSIS OF INFINITE SLOPES IN CLAY

The vertical stress σ_v acting on plane AB (Fig. 10.3) where

$$\sigma_v = \gamma z \cos \beta$$

is represented by OC in Fig. 3.1 in the stress diagram. The normal stress on this plane is OE and the shearing stress is EC. The line OC makes an angle β with the σ -axis. The Mohr strength envelope is represented by line FA whose equation is

$$S = c' + \sigma' \tan \phi'$$

According to the envelope, the shearing strength is ED where the normal stress is OE. When β is greater than ϕ' the lines OC and ED meet. In this case the two lines meet at A. As long as the shearing stress on a plane is less than the shearing strength on the plane, there is no danger of failure. Figure 10.3 indicates that at all depths at which the direct stress is less than OB, there is no possibility of failure. However at a particular depth at which the direct stress is OB, the

Figure 3.2.1 Stability analysis of infinite slopes in clay soils

shearing strength and shearing stress values are equal as represented by AB, failure is imminent. This depth at which the shearing stress and shearing strength are equal is called the critical depth. At depths greater than this critical value, Fig. 3.2.1 indicates that the shearing stress is greater than the shearing strength but this is not possible. Therefore it may be concluded that the slope may be steeper than ϕ' as long as the depth of the slope is less than the critical depth.

3.3 Expression for the Stability of an Infinite Slope of Clay of Depth H

Equation (2.1) gives the developed shearing stress as

$$\tau = C'_m + \sigma' \tan \phi'_m$$

Under conditions of no seepage and no pore pressure, the stress components on a plane at depth H and parallel to the surface of the slope are

$$\begin{aligned} \tau &= \gamma H \sin \beta \cos \beta \\ \sigma' &= \gamma H \cos^2 \beta \end{aligned}$$

Substituting these stress expressions in the equation above and simplifying, we have

$$\begin{aligned} C'_m &= \gamma H \cos^2 \beta (\tan \beta - \tan \phi'_m) \\ \text{Or } N_s &= \frac{C'_m}{\gamma H} = \cos^2 \beta (\tan \beta - \tan \phi'_m) \dots \dots \dots (3.1) \end{aligned}$$

where H is the allowable height and the term $\frac{C'_m}{\gamma} H$ is a dimensionless expression called the stability number and is designated as N_s . This dimensionless number is proportional to the

required cohesion and is inversely proportional to the allowable height. The solution is for the case when no seepage is occurring. If in Eq. (3.1) the factor of safety with respect to friction is unity, the stability number with respect to cohesion may be written as

$$N_s = \frac{c'}{F_c \gamma H} = \cos^2 \beta (\tan \beta - \tan \phi') \dots \dots \dots (3.2)$$

$$\text{Where } C'_m = \frac{c'}{F_c}$$

The stability number in Eq. (3.2) may be written as

$$N_s = \frac{C'_m}{F_c \gamma H} = \frac{C'_m}{\gamma H_c} \dots \dots \dots (3.3)$$

where H_c = critical height. From Eq. (3.3), we have

$$F_c = \frac{H_c}{H} = F_c \dots \dots \dots (3.4)$$

Eq. (3.4) indicates that the factor of safety with respect to cohesion, F_c , is the same as the factor of safety with respect to height FH .

If there is seepage parallel to the ground surface throughout the entire mass, with the free water surface coinciding with the ground surface, the components of effective stresses on planes

parallel to the surface of slopes at depth H are given as [Fig.3.2.2a].

Normal stress

$$\sigma'_n = (\gamma_{sat} - \gamma_w)H \cos^2 \beta = \gamma_b H \cos^2 \beta \dots \dots \dots (3.5)$$

the shearing stress

$$\tau = \gamma_{sat} H \sin \beta \cos \beta \dots \dots \dots (3.6)$$

Now substituting Eqs (3.5) and (3.6) into equation

$$\tau = C'_m + \sigma'_n \tan \phi'_m$$

and simplifying, the stability expression obtained is

$$\frac{C'_m}{\gamma_{sat} H} = \cos^2 \beta \tan \beta - \frac{\gamma_w}{\gamma_{sat}} \tan \phi'_m$$

Figure 3.2.2 Analysis of infinite slope (a) with seepage flow through the entire mass, and (b) with completely submerged slope.

As before, if the factor of safety with respect to friction is unity, the stability number which represents the cohesion may be written as

$$N_s = \frac{c'}{F_c \gamma_b H} = \frac{c'}{\gamma_b H_c} = \cos^2 \beta (\tan \beta - \tan \phi') \dots \dots \dots 3.7$$

If the slope is completely submerged, and if there is no seepage as in Fig. 3.2.2(b), then Eq. (3.7) becomes

$$N_s = \frac{C'}{F_c \gamma_b H} = \frac{C'}{\gamma_b H_c} = \cos^2 \beta (\tan \beta - \tan \phi')$$

where γ_b = submerged unit weight of the soil.

4. METHODS OF STABILITY ANALYSIS OF SLOPES OF FINITE HEIGHT

The stability of slopes of infinite extent has been discussed in previous sections. A more common problem is the one in which the failure occurs on curved surfaces. The most widely used method of analysis of homogeneous, isotropic, finite slopes is the Swedish method based on circular failure surfaces. Petterson (1955) first applied the circle method to the analysis of a soil failure in connection with the failure of a quarry wall in Goeteborg, Sweden. A Swedish National Commission, after studying a large number of failures, published a report in 1922 showing that the lines of failure of most such slides roughly approached the circumference of a circle. The failure circle might pass above the toe, through the toe or below it. By investigating the strength along the arc of a large number of such circles, it was possible to locate the circle which gave the lowest resistance to shear. This general method has been quite widely accepted as offering an approximately correct solution for the determination of the factor of safety of a slope of an embankment and of its foundation. Developments in the method of analysis have been made by Fellenius (1947), Terzaghi (1943), Gilboy (1934), Taylor (1937), Bishop (1955), and others, with the result that a satisfactory analysis of the stability of slopes, embankments and foundations by means of the circle method is no longer an unduly tedious procedure. There are other methods of historic interest such as the Culmann method (1875) and the logarithmic spiral method. The Culmann method assumes that rupture will occur along a plane. It is of interest only as a classical solution, since actual failure surfaces are invariably curved. This method is approximately correct for steep slopes. The logarithmic spiral method was recommended by Rendulic (1935) with the rupture surface assuming the shape of logarithmic spiral. Though this method makes the problem statically determinate and gives more accurate results, the greater length of time required for computation overbalances this accuracy. There are several methods of stability analysis based on the circular arc surface of failure. A few of the methods are described below.

Methods of Analysis

The majority of the methods of analysis may be categorized as limit equilibrium methods. The basic assumption of the limit equilibrium approach is that Coulomb's failure criterion is satisfied along the assumed failure surface. A free body is taken from the slope and starting from known or assumed values of the forces acting upon the free body, the shear resistance of the soil necessary for equilibrium is calculated. This calculated shear resistance is then compared to the estimated or available shear strength of the soil to give an indication of the factor of safety. Methods that consider only the whole free body are the (a) slope failure under undrained conditions, (b) friction-circle method (Taylor, 1937, 1948) and (c) Taylor's stability number (1948).

Methods that divide the free body into many vertical slices and consider the equilibrium of each slice are the Swedish circle method (Fellenius, 1927), Bishop method (1955), Bishop and Morgenstern method (1960) and Spencer method (1967). The majority of these methods are in chart form and cover a wide variety of conditions.

4.1 PLANE SURFACE OF FAILURE

Culmann (1875) assumed a plane surface of failure for the analysis of slopes which is mainly of interest because it serves as a test of the validity of the assumption of plane failure. In some cases this assumption is reasonable and in others it is questionable.

Figure 4.1 Stability of slopes by Culmann method

The method as indicated above assumes that the critical surface of failure is a plane surface passing through the toe of the dam as shown in Fig. 4.1

The forces that act on the mass above trial failure plane AC inclined at angle β with the horizontal are shown in the figure. The expression for the weight, W , and the total cohesion C are respectively,

$$W = \frac{1}{2} \gamma L H \operatorname{cosec} \beta \sin(\beta - \theta)$$

and $C = C' L$

The use of the law of sines in the force triangle, shown in the figure, gives

$$\frac{C}{W} = \frac{\sin(\theta - \phi')}{\cos \phi'}$$

Substituting herein for C and W , and rearranging we have

$$\frac{C'}{\gamma H} = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{cosec} \beta \sin(\beta - \theta) \sec \phi'$$

in which the subscript θ indicates that the stability number is for the trial plane at inclination θ . The most dangerous plane is obtained by setting the first derivative of the above equation with respect to θ equal to zero. This operation gives

$$\theta'_c = \frac{1}{2} (\beta + \phi')$$

where θ'_c is the critical angle for limiting equilibrium and the stability number for limiting equilibrium may be written as

$$\frac{C'}{\gamma H_c} = \frac{1 - \cos(\beta - \phi')}{4 \sin \beta \cos \phi'} \dots \dots \dots (4.1)$$

where H_c is the critical height of the slope. If we write

$$F_c = \frac{C'}{C'_m}, F_\phi = \frac{\tan \phi'}{\tan \phi'_m}$$

where F_c and F_ϕ are safety factors with respect to cohesion and friction respectively, Eq. (4.1) may be modified for chosen values of C'_m and ϕ'_m as

$$\frac{C'_m}{\gamma H} = \frac{1 - \cos(\beta - \phi'_m)}{4 \sin \beta \cos \phi'_m} \dots \dots \dots (4.2)$$

The critical angle for any assumed values of C'_m and ϕ'_m is

$$\theta_c = \frac{1}{2}(\beta + \phi'_m)$$

From Eq. (4.2), the allowable height of a slope is

$$H = \frac{4C'_m \sin\beta \cos\phi'_m}{\gamma[1 - \cos(\beta - \phi'_m)]}$$

4.2 CIRCULAR SURFACES OF FAILURE

The investigations carried out in Sweden at the beginning of this century have clearly confirmed that the surfaces of failure of earth slopes resemble the shape of a circular arc. When soil slips along a circular surface, such a slide may be termed as a rotational slide. It involves downward and outward movement of a slice of earth as shown in Fig. 4.2.1(a) and sliding occurs along the entire surface of contact between the slice and its base. The types of failure that normally occur may be classified as

1. Slope failure
2. Toe failure
3. Base failure

In slope failure, the arc of the rupture surface meets the slope above the toe. This can happen when the slope angle β is quite high and the soil close to the toe possesses high strength. Toe failure occurs when the soil mass of the dam above the base and below the base is homogeneous. The base failure occurs particularly when the base angle β is low and the soil below the base is softer and more plastic than the soil above the base. The various modes of failure are shown in Fig. 4.2.1.

Figure 4.2.1 Types of failure of earth dams

4.3 FAILURE UNDER UNDRAINED CONDITIONS ($\phi_u = 0$)

A fully saturate immediately after construction. The stability analysis is based on the assumption that the soil is homogeneous

and the potential failure surface is a circular arc. Two types of failures considered are

1. Slope failure
2. Base failure

The undrained shear strength C_u of soil is assumed to be constant with depth. A trial failure circular surface AB with center at O and radius R is shown in Fig. 4.3.1(a) for a toe failure. The slope AC and the chord AB make angles β and α with the horizontal respectively. W is the weight per unit

Figure 4.3.1 Critical circle positions for (a) slope failure (after Fellenius, 1927), (b) base failure

Figure 4.3.2 (a) Relation between slope angle β and parameters α and θ for location of critical toe circle when β is greater than 53° ; (b) relation between slope angle β and depth factor n_d for various values of parameter n_x (after Fellenius, 1927)

length of the soil lying above the trial surface acting through the center of gravity of the mass. l_0 is the lever arm, L_a is the length of the arc, L_c the length of the chord AB and C_m the mobilized cohesion for any assumed surface of failure.

We may express the factor of safety F_s as

$$F_s = \frac{C_u}{C_m} \dots \dots \dots 4.3.1$$

For equilibrium of the soil mass lying above the assumed failure surface, we may write

resisting moment $M_r =$ actuating moment M_a

The resisting moment $M_r = l_a C_m R$

Actuating moment, $M_a = W l_o$

Equation for the mobilized C_m is

$$C_m = \frac{W l_o}{l_a R}$$

Now the factor of safety F for the assumed trial arc of failure may be determined from Eq. (4.3.1). This is for one trial arc. The procedure has to be repeated for several trial arcs and the one that gives the least value is the critical circle.

If failure occurs along a toe circle, the center of the critical circle can be located by laying off the angles α and 2θ shown in Fig. 4.3.1(a). Values of a and b for different slope angles β can be obtained from Fig. 4.3.2(a). If there is a base failure as shown in Fig. 4.3.1(b), the trial circle will be tangential to the firm base and as such the center of the critical circle lies on the vertical line passing through midpoint M on slope AC. The following equations may be written with reference to Fig. 4.3.1(b).

Depth factor $n_d = \frac{D}{H}$ Distance factor, $n_x = \frac{x}{H}$

Values of n_x can be estimated for different values of n_d and β by means of the chart Fig. 4.3.2(b).

5. TAYLOR'S STABILITY NUMBER FOR THE STABILITY

If the slope angle β , height of embankment H, the effective unit weight of material γ , angle of internal friction ϕ' , and unit cohesion C' are known, the factor of safety may be determined. In order to make unnecessary the more or less tedious stability determinations, Taylor (1937) conceived the idea of analyzing the stability of a large number of slopes through a wide range of slope angles and angles of internal friction, and then representing the results by an abstract number which he called the "stability number". This number is designated as N_s . The expression used is

$$N_s = \frac{C'}{F_c \gamma H}$$

From this the factor of safety with respect to cohesion may be expressed as

$$F_c = \frac{C'}{N_s \gamma H}$$

Taylor published his results in the form of curves which give the relationship between N_s and the slope angles β for various values of ϕ' as shown in Fig. 5.1. These curves are for circles passing through the toe, although for values of β less than 53° , it has been found that the most dangerous circle passes below the toe. However, these curves may be used without serious error for slopes down to $\beta = 14^\circ$. The stability numbers are obtained for factors of safety with respect to cohesion by keeping the factor of safety with respect to friction (F_ϕ) equal to unity.

In slopes encountered in practical problems, the depth to which the rupture circle may extend is usually limited by ledge or other underlying strong material as shown in Fig. 5.2. The stability number N_s for the case when $\phi' = 0$ is greatly dependent on the position of the ledge. The depth at which the ledge or strong material occurs may be expressed in terms of a depth factor N_d which is defined as

$$n_d = \frac{D}{H}$$

where D = depth of ledge below the top of the embankment, H = height of slope above the toe. For various values of n_d and for the $\phi' = 0$ case the chart in Fig. 5.2 gives the stability number N_s for various values of slope angle β . In this case the rupture circle may pass through the toe or below the toe.

Figure 5.1 Taylor's stability numbers for circles passing through the toe and below or above the toe (After Taylor's 1937)

The distance X of the rupture circle from the toe at the toe level may be expressed by a distance factor n_x which is defined as

$$n_x = \frac{x}{H}$$

The chart in Fig. 5.2 shows the relationship between n_d and n_x . If there is a ledge or other stronger material at the elevation of the toe, the depth factor n_d for this case is unity.

Figure 5.2 Taylor's stability numbers for $\phi = 0$ case (After Taylor's 1937)

5.1 Factor of Safety with Respect to Strength

The development of the stability number is based on the assumption that the factor of safety with respect to friction F_ϕ is unity. The curves give directly the factor of safety F_c with respect to cohesion only. If a true factor of safety F_s with respect to strength is required, this factor should apply equally to both cohesion and friction. The mobilized shear strength may therefore be expressed as

$$S_m = \frac{S}{F_s} = \frac{C'}{F_s} + \frac{\sigma' \tan \phi'}{F_s}$$

In the above expression, we may write

$$\frac{C'}{F_s} = C'_m, \quad \tan \phi'_m = \frac{\tan \phi'}{F_s}, \quad \phi'_m = \frac{\phi'}{F_s}$$

C'_m and ϕ'_m may be described as average values of mobilized cohesion and friction respectively.

5.2 TENSION CRACKS

If a dam is built of cohesive soil, tension cracks are usually present at the crest. The depth of such cracks may be computed from the equation

$$Z_0 = \frac{2C'}{\gamma}$$

where Z_0 = depth of crack, C' = unit cohesion, γ = unit weight of soil.

The effective length of any trial arc of failure is the difference between the total length of arc minus the depth of crack as shown in Fig. 5.2.1.

Figure 5.2.1 Tension crack in dams built of cohesive soils

6. STABILITY ANALYSIS BY METHOD OF SLICES FOR STEADY SEEPAGE

The stability analysis with steady seepage involves the development of the pore pressure head diagram along the chosen trial circle of failure. The simplest of the methods for knowing the pore pressure head at any point on the trial circle is by the use of flownets which is described below.

6.1 Determination of Pore Pressure with Seepage

Figure 6.1.1 shows the section of a homogeneous dam with an arbitrarily chosen trial arc. There is steady seepage flow through the dam as represented by flow and equipotential lines. From the equipotential lines the pore pressure may be obtained at any point on the section. For example at point a in Fig. 6.1.1 the pressure head is h . Point c is determined by setting the radial distance ac

Figure 6.1.1 Determination of pore pressure with steady seepage.

equal to h . A number of points obtained in the same manner as c give the curved line through c which is a pore pressure head diagram.

6.2 Method of Analysis (graphical method)

Figure 6.2.1(a) shows the section of a dam with an arbitrarily chosen trial arc. The center of rotation of the arc is O . The pore pressure acting on the base of the arc as obtained from flow nets is shown in Fig. 6.2.1(b).

When the soil forming the slope has to be analyzed under a condition where full or partial drainage takes place the analysis must take into account both cohesive and frictional soil properties based on effective stresses. Since the effective stress acting across each elemental length of the assumed circular arc failure surface must be computed in this case, the method of slices is one of the convenient methods for this purpose. The method of analysis is as follows.

The soil mass above the assumed slip circle is divided into a number of vertical slices of equal width. The number of slices may be limited to a maximum of eight to ten to facilitate computation. The forces used in the analysis acting on the slices are shown in Figs. 6.2.1(a) and (c). The forces are:

1. The weight W of the slice.
2. The normal and tangential components of the weight W acting on the base of the slice. They are designated respectively as N and T .
3. The pore water pressure U acting on the base of the slice.
4. The effective frictional and cohesive resistances acting on the base of the slice which is designated as S .

The forces acting on the sides of the slices are statically indeterminate as they depend on the stress deformation properties of the material, and we can make only gross assumptions about their relative magnitudes. In the conventional slice method of analysis the lateral forces are assumed equal on both sides of the slice. This assumption is not strictly correct. The error due to this assumption on the mass as a whole is about 15 percent (Bishop, 1955).

(a) Total normal and tangential components

Figure 6.2.1 Stability analysis of slope by the method of slices.

The forces that are actually considered in the analysis are shown in Fig. 6.2.1(c). The various components may be determined as follows:

1. The weight, W , of a slice per unit length of dam may be computed from

$$W = \gamma hb$$

where, γ = total unit weight of soil, h = average height of slice, b = width of slice. If the widths of all slices are equal, and if the whole mass is homogeneous, the weight W can be plotted as a vector AB passing through the center of a slice as in Fig. 6.2.1(a). AB may be made equal to the height of the slice.

2. By constructing triangle ABC , the weight can be resolved into a normal component N and a tangential component T . Similar triangles can be constructed for all slices. The tangential components of the weights cause the mass to slide downward. The sum of all the weights cause the mass to slide downward. The sum of all the tangential components may be expressed as

$$T_1 = \sum T$$

If the trial surface is curved upward near its lower end, the tangential component of the weight of the slice will act in the opposite direction along the curve. The algebraic sum of T should be considered.

3. The average pore pressure u acting on the base of any slice of length l may be found from the pore pressure diagram shown in Fig. 6.2.1 (b). The total pore pressure, U , on the base of any slice is

$$U = ul$$

4. The effective normal pressure N' acting on the base of any slice is

$$N' = N - U \quad [\text{Fig. 6.2.1(c)}]$$

5. The frictional force F' acting on the base of any slice resisting the tendency of the slice to move downward is $F = (N - U) \tan \phi'$

where ϕ' is the effective angle of friction. Similarly the cohesive force C' opposing the movement of the slice and acting at the base of the slice is $C' = c'l$

where c is the effective unit cohesion. The total resisting force S acting on the base of the slice is

$S = C' + F = c'l + (N - U) \tan \phi'$ Figure 6.2.1(c) shows the resisting forces acting on the base of a slice.

The sum of all the resisting forces acting on the base of each slice may be expressed as

$$S_s = c' \sum l + \tan \phi' \sum (N - U) = c'L + \tan \phi' \sum (N - U)$$

where $\sum l = L =$ length of the curved surface.

The moments of the acting and resisting forces about the point of rotation may be written as follows:

$$\text{Actuating moment} = R \sum T$$

$$\text{Resisting moment} = R [c'L + \tan \phi' \sum (N - U)]$$

The factor of safety F_s may now be written as

$$F_s = \frac{[c'L + \tan \phi' \sum (N - U)]}{\sum T} \dots \dots \dots 6.2.1$$

The various components shown in Eq. (6.2.1) can easily be represented graphically as shown in Fig. 6.2.1(d). The line AB represents to a suitable scale $\sum (N - U)$. BC is drawn normal to AB at B and equal to $c'L + \tan \phi' \sum (N - U)$. The line AD drawn at an angle ϕ' to AB gives the intercept BD on BC equal to $\phi' \sum (N - U)$. The length BE on BC is equal to $\sum T$ Now

$$F_s = \frac{BC}{BE}$$

7. Numerical methods of analysis

Numerical modelling techniques provide an approximate solution to problems which otherwise cannot be solved by conventional methods, e.g. complex geometry, material anisotropy, non-linear behavior, in situ stresses. Numerical analysis allows for material deformation and failure, modelling of pore pressures, creep deformation, dynamic loading, assessing effects of parameter variations etc. However, numerical modelling is restricted by some limitations. For example, input parameters are not usually measured and availability of these data is generally poor. User also should be aware of boundary effects, meshing errors, hardware memory and time restrictions. Numerical methods used for slope stability analysis can be divided into three main groups: continuum, discontinuum and hybrid modeling.

7.1 Continuum modeling

Modelling of the continuum is suitable for the analysis of soil slopes, massive intact rock or heavily jointed rock masses. This approach includes the finite-difference and *finite element* methods that discretize the whole mass to finite number of elements with the help of generated mesh (Fig. 7.1). In finite-difference method (FDM) differential equilibrium equations (i.e. strain-displacement and stress-strain relations) are solved. *finite element* method (FEM) uses the approximations to the connectivity of elements, continuity of displacements and stresses between elements. Most of numerical codes allows modelling of discrete fractures, e.g. bedding planes, faults. Several constitutive models are usually available, e.g. elasticity, elasto-plasticity, strain-softening, elasto-viscoplasticity etc

Figure 7.1 Finite element mesh

7.2 Discontinuum modeling

Discontinuum approach is useful for rock slopes controlled by discontinuity behaviour. Rock mass is considered as an aggregation of distinct, interacting blocks subjected to external loads and assumed to undergo motion with time. This methodology is collectively called the discrete-element method (DEM). Discontinuum modelling allows for sliding between the blocks or particles. The DEM is based on solution of dynamic equation of equilibrium for each block repeatedly until the boundary conditions and laws of contact and motion are satisfied. Discontinuum modelling belongs to the most commonly applied numerical approach to rock slope analysis and following variations of the DEM exist.

- distinct-element method
- discontinuous deformation analysis (DDA)
- particle flow codes

The distinct-element approach describes mechanical behaviour of both, the discontinuities and the solid material. This methodology is based on a force-displacement law (specifying the interaction between the deformable rock blocks) and a law of motion (determining displacements caused in the blocks by out-of-balance forces). Joints are treated as [boundary conditions. Deformable blocks are discretized into internal constant-strain elements.

Discontinuum program **UDEC** (Universal distinct element code) is suitable for high jointed rock slopes subjected to static or dynamic loading. Two-dimensional analysis of translational failure mechanism allows for simulating large displacements, modelling deformation or material yielding. Three-dimensional discontinuum code **3DEC** contains modelling of multiple intersecting discontinuities and therefore it is suitable for analysis of wedge instabilities or influence of rock support (e.g. rockbolts, cables)

In discontinuous deformation analysis (DDA) displacements are unknowns and equilibrium equations are then solved analogous to finite element method. Each unit of finite element type mesh represents an isolated block bounded by discontinuities. Advantage of this methodology is possibility to model large deformations, rigid body movements, coupling or failure states between rock blocks.

Discontinuous rock mass can be modelled with the help of distinct-element methodology in the form of *particle flow* code, e.g. program **PFC2D/3D**. Spherical particles interact through

frictional sliding contacts. Simulation of joint bounded blocks may be realized through specified bond strengths. Law of motion is repeatedly applied to each particle and force-displacement law to each contact. *Particle flow* methodology enables modelling of granular flow, fracture of intact rock, transitional block movements, dynamic response to blasting or seismicity, deformation between particles caused by shear or tensile forces. These codes also allow to model subsequent failure processes of rock slope, e.g. simulation of rock.

7.2 Hybrid/coupled modeling

Hybrid codes involve the coupling of various methodologies to maximize their key advantages, e.g. *limit equilibrium* analysis combined with *finite element* groundwater flow and stress analysis ; coupled *particle flow* and finite-difference analyses. Hybrid techniques allows investigation of piping slope failures and the influence of high groundwater pressures on the failure of weak rock slope. Coupled *finite*-/distinct elements codes provide for the modelling of both intact rock behavior and the development and behavior of fractures.

8. CONCLUSION

This paper aims an overview on various methods of slope stability on the basis of assumptions, Factor of safety calculation, applicability of output of the method with its limitations. This paper also aims to focus some new mathematical tools which can be applicable for stability analysis of slope and finite element methods in slope stability analysis based on significant works by numerous authors have been done with regards to stability of slopes. Various parameters and factor of safety equations used by them have been reviewed and discussed briefly. Some mathematical tools are also suggested which can be used for analysis of slope in particular condition.

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